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Increasing frequency of geomorphic disasters: climate change or geomorphic change?

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Different types of data obtained by the authors in the last 20 years have led to the formulation of some concepts and a hypothesis related to the present evolution of geomorphic processes. Data gathered included landslide frequency, sedimentation rates, river discharge, rainfall and different indicators of human influence on land surface. Results obtained indicate that there is an important and growing *human geomorphic footprint*, which is causing a *global geomorphic change* reflected by the intensification of geomorphic processes. Geomorphic processes' intensification appears to be a characteristic of the Anthropocene, and is particularly marked since mid-20th century, coinciding with the great demographic and economic post World War II expansion. This "great geomorphic acceleration" does not seem to respond to climate change, but to human modification of land surface. A hypothesis, based on the driving force-pressure-state-impact-response conceptual model, was formulated to explain the results indicated.

If the hypothesis were correct, human influence and global geomorphic change should be reflected differently in the different types of natural hazards and risks. The number of all types of natural disasters registered in databases should be expected to increase with time, due to both growing human exposure and better data-gathering. Seismic and volcanic disasters should increase least. Climatic disasters, affected by the greater frequency of extreme events related to climate change, should increase more. Finally, geomorphic disasters, affected by both climate and geomorphic change, should increase most. Global data on the frequency of those disasters are presented and compared with data on potential natural and human drivers. The results obtained are to a very great extent coherent with the hypothesis and reinforce the idea that mitigation of geomorphic disasters should not focus mainly on climate, but rather on land-use issues.

Geomorphic risk assessment and management in the context of global change

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Natural disasters due to geomorphic processes appear to be growing in most regions of the world. This is often considered to be a consequence of climate change. Geomorphic hazard and risk management are strongly dependent on our ability to appropriately assess future frequency of potentially dangerous geomorphic events. This, in turn, depends on our knowledge of past trends and understanding of factors that determine them. Global, continental and regional data on the frequency of hydrogeomorphic disasters during the last century are presented and compared with potential natural (rainfall) and human (activities that modify land surface) drivers. Data so far available suggest that there is a marked increase in the frequency of those disasters from around the middle of last century. Of course, there is small doubt that intense rainfall is the main immediate trigger of floods and landslides, but precipitation does not seem to explain their growing frequency. Comparisons and correlations between disaster frequency and potential drivers suggest that climate change plays a minor role in the intensification of geomorphic processes and that the observed increase is caused mainly by the alteration of the surface layer. In other words, they seem to be driven by "global geomorphic change". This change reduces surface layer resilience and enhances geomorphic processes in general. Indeed, land surface modification and consequent increase in the intensity of geomorphic processes appear to be one of the characteristics of the Anthropocene.

As the magnitude of geomorphic change is directly linked to population and economic growth, it is reasonable to assume that trends observed during the last century will continue during the present one. Therefore, it is important to verify the proposed hypothesis. If it were correct, to find clues for better managing geomorphic hazards in the future we should not look up to the clouds, but down to the ground.

Landslide risk models on the basis of recent occurrences

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Mass movements, or landslides, are one of the most common and frequent processes affecting the Earth's surface. This type of process produces important economic losses when affecting vulnerable elements. Therefore, it is necessary to develop methods and/or tools that make possible risk assessment and prediction mapping for these processes. During recent decades significant progresses have been made in this field, developing and applying different methodologies to model landslide susceptibility and hazard. However, procedures for landslide risk modelling are scarce.

The occurrence of landslides in the Bajo Deva area (Guipúzcoa province, Spain) has been studied at length. For this reason a complete inventory of shallow landslides in the zone for the last 60 years has been obtained. In a lesser extent, data on landslide damage could be obtained.

In this work the economic losses caused by two landslides occurred in the study area due to heavy precipitations have been analysed. The study of these slope movements and their effects has been compared with landslide susceptibility, hazard and risk models elaborated in previous works.

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